

**IN DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION CONDITIONS
CYBER SECURITY NEEDS AND PRIORITIES****Samijonov is the son of Azizbek Ismailjon**

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Abstract: this article analyzes the essence and conceptual foundations of the concept of cyber security and the emerging risks and threats associated with digitization in the third millennium.

Keywords: digital technologies, cyber security, security, information security, threat, cyber war.

Rapid penetration of digital technologies into our lives is changing the way of life and conditions of humanity to a completely new level. The use of them in daily work and production has brought humanity to the fourth industrial revolution. This industrial revolution, based on the digital revolution, means a complete transition to automated production controlled by intelligent systems. In the conditions of such an industrial revolution, the issue of training highly qualified specialists who not only use digital technologies, but also produce them, is one of the problems facing the whole world. Of course, for any society faced with such a process, one of the priority issues is the preparation of future specialists who can manage the digital world and develop the digital economy. In our country, education of young people who have digital knowledge, thinking, can think strategically [1], who think independently and logically based on modern knowledge and experiences, national and universal values [2] is one of the priorities. This issue places great responsibility on the field of education.

In this period of transition to the fourth industrial revolution, the issue of educating young people requires us to pay attention to the work and scientific research that is being carried out in the world. The analysis of most of the literature shows that creative thinking, problem solving, critical thinking, and cooperation skills are necessary for a person of the 21st century. It can be found in many foreign scientific sources that these skills are the skills that make up rational thinking.

In the second half of the 20th century, it was discovered by psychologists that the ways of working with computers affect human thinking processes, that is, thinking. In modern conditions, mental activity mediated by computer technologies and changed by them requires a significant progress in the study of

social thinking, a new important object of psychological research [3]. Thinking as a psychological process begins in the context of a problematic situation.

The creation and development of computers is the result of solving various district problems. The process of working on them, creating programs for them and creating artificial intelligence certainly did not fail to have an impact on the cognitive characteristics of a person.

Academician A.P., the founder of computer science of the Soviet Union, who emphasized that programming is the second literacy. Ershov predicted that digital technologies will have an impact on the development of the intellectual potential of mankind, the quality of education, the basic rules of the theory and practice of teaching [4]. Years later, the opinions expressed by scientists are being proven.

The introduction of the concept of digital thinking into science began in the 50-60s of the 20th century under the name of algorithmic thinking. Algorithmic thinking is seen as the mental activity of posing a problem, feeding it to a machine with appropriate modifications to the output, and finding algorithms to perform these modifications³. By the 1980s, the American scientist Seymour Papert associated it with rote sexual thinking. According to him, "Procedural thinking involves step-by-step instructions for developing, presenting, testing, and adapting procedures, and each of these step-by-step instructions is translated into a formal form and executed by a special computer or automated device" [5]. This definition is close to the definition given to algorithmic thinking, but reflects a broader concept.

The term Computational Thinking (Computational Thinking or Vychislitelnoe myshlenie) was introduced by Janette Wing in 2006, and according to her: "Computational thinking is a thought process aimed at solving a problem and its possible solutions in a convenient form by an expert in the relevant field or by a computer"[6] done After some time, in 2011, J. Wing gives a new definition based on future research: "Digital thinking is a thinking process involved in formulating problems, solving them, and describing the solutions to problems in a form that can be solved by information processing tools."

At the moment, this concept has been interpreted differently by many researchers and has not been reduced to a standard explanation. However, research scholars focus on the development of the skills that make up digital thinking in learners and its introduction into the educational process rather than a comprehensive explanation of digital thinking. Of course, the definition and content of digital thinking are defined differently by researchers. N.D. Berman[7]

and K. Kansular[8] in their scientific articles explained the definition of digital thinking given by various scientists and researchers and its components. We will try to study and describe the definitions of digital thinking given by the authors in this literature. Therefore, digital thinking is a cognitive activity formed in the process of solving problems and issues with the help of computers and technical tools.

We will also try to summarize the components of digital thinking presented in the studied sources. So, we can say that digital thinking consists of the following: abstraction - eases the understanding of a problem or system, abstraction leads to simpler solutions; decomposition - a method of dividing problems into small and understandable components; algorithmic thinking - the process of creating a scheme of successive steps leading to the solution of the problem; automation - application of algorithms formed for efficient solution of other problems in computers and technical devices; generalization (evaluation) - the process of adapting formed solutions and algorithms to problems of different types. A method of quickly solving a new problem based on a previously known solution.

It can be seen from these founders of digital thinking that when finding a solution to a complex problem, it can be simplified into a simple solution without taking into account unnecessary elements, making them more understandable, using a sequence and applying it to a computer, as well as being able to apply it to a new problem. It will certainly be a great impetus to the development of cognitive activity. After all, a person performs a sequence of the above actions in order to achieve the desired result during his life. (For example, the well-known tea brewing algorithm). Therefore, the use of digital thinking in the educational process has a positive effect on its cognitive activity and helps learners to creatively solve problems and systematically receive various information.

The term "digital" means "active use of information technologies" in all fields. If in the ordinary economy material goods are considered the main resource, in the digital economy it will be processed and transmitted information, data" [9]. After their analysis, a proper management solution is developed. The digital economy is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is a modern stage of development, which is characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits. Secondly, the digital economy is a unique concept, the object of its study is the information society.

Digital technology was founded about 100 years ago with the use of wireless electronic communications. Telegraph messages and radio transmission devices are examples of our thinking. Since then, technology has advanced rapidly, resulting in radio recording, film, television, computers, CDs, and the Internet.[10] Digital technology has become a very useful tool for instant messaging and keeping people informed about local and international news. This, in turn, entered the educational system, like all areas of society, and had a great impact on its formation and development.

From the second half of the 20th century, the foundation was laid for the formation of new - Digital technologies, which eliminate transmission errors and effectively perform the same task by converting analog signals to digital signals.

Digital technology has been around for over 50 years and is widely used in computers and other electronic equipment. Beginning in the early 1960s, teachers and computer scientists began using computers for educational purposes. Initially, it was used only for reading and writing to provide instructions on how to use the computer, and later to solve some time-consuming problems, since the interaction between users and the computer was not high. However, with the invention of inexpensive microcomputers and the integration of text, graphics, and color, computers quickly spread to businesses, schools, and homes.[11] Ultimately, opportunities for using digital technologies in education have expanded.

Today, digital technologies are becoming an integral part of development in many countries of the world and their importance in improving the educational process and its effectiveness as part of ensuring a more sustainable future.

In the information environment with a complex system, the process component is distinguished as its dynamic and changing part - information-communication processes, which actively affect individual, group and social psychology (in particular, individual, group and public consciousness). As a confirmation of our opinion, the Russian scientist G.V. We quote Grachev's opinion: "To a certain extent, the spiritual sphere of society is directly affected by the information environment, its deformation and destructive changes in the form of psycho-emotional and social stress, broken moral standards and criteria, incorrect social stereotypes and guidelines, false goals and values, in turn, it affects processes and situations in the main spheres of social, including political and economic life" [12].

In modern times, scientists and specialists of advanced countries have developed many doctrines and views in this field, in addition to information

security, and research is being conducted on their practice.[13] From this point of view, researches from economic, technical, socio-cultural and philosophical point of view are of priority in studying the problems related to the information society and determining promising directions. According to the American philosopher Daniel Bell, the started information revolution consists of two revolutions: the computer revolution and the telecommunications revolution, as a result of which the technology was created that made information the central link of all social life, especially economic life[14].

In conclusion, in order not to get attached to information, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the source of information. It is necessary to make sure of the reliability (scientific, spiritual, cultural), correctness (including historical) of the offered information. For this, acquiring knowledge, teaching to compare the proposed information with previously known information, and to selectively accept information is an important pedagogical problem.

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